

Unraveling the role of Ti in the stability of positive layered oxide electrodes for rechargeable Na-ion batteries

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The many advantages of Na-ion batteries (NIBs) in terms of availability and cost of raw materials compared with Li-ion batteries (LIBs) are hindered by the stability of Na-based electrodes. The most promising NIB positive electrodes are Co- and Ni-free sodium manganese rich layered oxides with the general formula $\text{Na}_x\text{Mn}_{1-y}\text{TM}_y\text{T}'\text{M}_z\text{O}_2$ ($y < 0.33$, TM = transition metal/s). Although their stability is greatly improved when doped with electrochemically inactive species such as Mg or Ti, the rationale behind this has not been understood to date. Here, we demonstrate how a given degree of Ti^{IV} doping ($z = 0.1$) helps to stabilize the crystal structure of sodium manganese rich layered oxides by absorbing electrochemically induced strain; a remarkable step forward on the quest of finding the best NIB positive electrode. In this case, any Mn–Ti substitution below $z = 0.1$ will not be enough to absorb the strain and substitutions above this value will increase the amount of Jahn–Teller active Mn^{III} leading to destabilization of the crystal structure with poor electrochemical performance. The possibility of controlling structural and electrochemical properties by TM substitution is the starting point towards the design of electrode materials that will ultimately lead towards competitive Na-ion batteries.

1. Introduction

The revolution in portable electronics, power tools, electric transportation and grid storage initiated by the advent of Li-ion batteries (LIBs) could come to a halt due to three main factors inherent to the nature of LIBs, namely natural abundance and uneven distribution of Li worldwide,¹ as well as the ubiquitous presence of Co and Ni in the vast majority of LIB positive electrode materials, which are key points that directly strike the cost and environmental impact of LIBs.^{2,3} In recent years, the development of Na-ion batteries (NIBs) has positioned them as a feasible alternative to LIBs, particularly for certain applications where cost and availability of raw materials could be an issue.^{4–10}

46 However, the cycling stability of NIBs and in particular several positive electrode
47 materials hinders the outburst of this technology. Therefore, understanding the driving
48 factors behind electrode stability is crucial for obtaining competitive NIBs that can
49 outperform Li-ion technology. Co- and Ni-free positive electrodes based on sodium
50 manganese rich layered oxides ($\text{Na}_x\text{Mn}_{1-y}\text{TM}_y\text{O}_2$, $y < 0.33$, TM = transition metal/s) have
51 recently attracted great attention,^{11,12} mainly due to their outstanding electrochemical
52 performance and the presence of Mn as the main electroactive transition metal.^{13–15} Mn
53 is a nontoxic, abundant and low-cost element with a number of different oxidation
54 states, which enables the synthesis of active materials whose redox voltages can be
55 conveniently tuned ($\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}$ is the most used redox couple in layered oxides).¹²

56
57 The two main drawbacks that affect the electrochemical performance of layered oxides
58 are the dissolution of Mn in the electrolyte and the Jahn–Teller (JT) distortion associated
59 with high spin Mn^{III} ($(t2g)^3(e^*g)^1$ (Fig. 1a)).^{12,16} Protecting the active material surface¹⁷
60 and doping with electrochemically inactive species such as Mg^{13,18–21} or Ti^{14,15} are the
61 two main strategies that have been proposed to mitigate the previously mentioned
62 issues. In spite of the practical success after applying these strategies, the exact
63 mechanisms behind their effectiveness are not fully understood yet. This is particularly
64 so in the case of doping with electrochemically inactive species. Among the different
65 possibilities, Ti doping is an especially intriguing paradigmatic case. Whilst $\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{–Ti}^{\text{IV}}$
66 substitution facilitates the deinsertion/insertion of Na^+ ion by the increase of the Na
67 interlayer distance,^{22–25} as suggested by some authors, it also seems to induce TM
68 disorder which improve reversibility upon cycling.²⁶ However, when JT-active Mn^{III} is
69 partially substituted by Ti^{IV} , it has been agreed that the overall structure is stabilized.
70 But, if the Ti substitution increases beyond a threshold value, a negative effect is
71 observed on the electrochemistry.^{22,27} No investigation to date has provided a clear
72 explanation of the role of Ti doping or JT distortion in structure stabilization and its
73 relationship with the electrochemical behaviour of Mn rich layered oxides. In fact, there
74 is still an open question about how Ti stabilizes the structure of the layered oxide if the
75 presence of Ti^{IV} increases the amount of high spin Mn^{III} leading to a higher JT distortion.

76
77 Herein, for the first time, we report the role that Ti^{IV} plays in controlling JT distortion in
78 $\text{P2–Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1, \text{ and } 0.2$) which is the driver for the material's
79 stability upon electrochemical cycling. We identified the optimum Ti^{IV} doping level that
80 leads to the best electrochemical performance which is a balance between Ti^{IV}
81 octahedra absorbing electrochemical induced strain and minimizing the amount of JT-
82 active Mn^{III} resulting from excess doping with Ti^{IV} , which is certainly crucial knowledge
83 that would enable the advent of commercial NIBs.

84 85 2. Experimental

86 2.1. Synthesis of $\text{P2–Na}_{2/3}[\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}]\text{O}_2$, $\text{P2–Na}_{2/3}[\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.1}]\text{O}_2$ and P2– 87 $\text{Na}_{2/3}[\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Ti}_{0.2}]\text{O}_2$

88 The three samples were synthesized by the ceramic method. The synthesis of P2–
89 $\text{Na}_{2/3}[\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}]\text{O}_2$ (herein referred to as MnFe) and $\text{P2–Na}_{2/3}[\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_{0.1}]\text{O}_2$ (herein
90 referred to as MnFeTi) has been already reported by our group^{14,28} while the P2–
91 $\text{Na}_{2/3}[\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Ti}_{0.2}]\text{O}_2$ (herein referred to as MnTi) sample was synthesized by mixing

92 anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (Sharlab), Mn₂O₃ (Alfa Aesar) and TiO₂ (Alfa Aesar) in a stoichiometric
93 amount, pelletizing and heating up to 1000 °C under atmospheric conditions for 10
94 hours. Once synthesized the samples were transferred to an Ar-filled glove box in order
95 to avoid contact with the atmosphere.

96

97 2.2. Structural characterization

98 Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns were collected using a Bruker Discover D8
99 instrument with Cu radiation (Cu K $\alpha_{1,2}$ = 1.540530 Å) in the 2 θ range of 10–80°. The
100 samples were covered with a Kapton film in order to record the PXRD patterns in a
101 protected atmosphere. The PXRD patterns were refined using FullProf Suite software²⁹
102 and the crystal structure was drawn using VESTA software.³⁰

103

104 2.3. Local structure and chemical environment

105 Mn and Ti K-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) spectra were collected at the
106 XAFS beamline of the Elettra synchrotron radiation facility (Trieste, Italy).³¹ The X-ray
107 beam delivered by a bending magnet source was monochromatized by using a Si (111)
108 double-crystal monochromator. Higher order harmonics were rejected by detuning the
109 second crystal of the monochromator by 40% with respect to the maximum of the
110 rocking curve. Finely ground sample powders were mixed with carboxymethyl cellulose
111 (CMC) in a suitable amount to carry out measurements in transmission mode, pressed
112 into pellets and sealed in a Kapton foil to avoid air contamination. Spectra were collected
113 at room temperature using two ionization chambers to measure the incident and
114 transmitted flux. The energy was calibrated by setting the first inflection point of the
115 absorption spectrum of Mn and Ti metal to 6539 eV and 4966 eV respectively. Spectra
116 from reference metal foils were recorded simultaneously with all the sample spectra
117 using a third ion chamber to monitor the energy scale between different scans.
118 Extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) analysis was carried out by using the
119 GNXAS package,^{32,33} using standard procedures.

120

121 2.4. Electrochemical characterization

122 Laminates were prepared in an Ar-filled glove box using the active material, carbon
123 Super C65 (Timcal) and PVDF ([poly(vinylidene difluoride)], Solef) dissolved in NMP
124 (N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone) in a mass ratio of 80:10:10. The slurry was cast on battery grade
125 Al foil and dried under vacuum at 120 °C for 12 hours. 12 mm diameter electrodes were
126 pressed at 4 tons before assembling the cells in an Ar glove box, with a mass loading of
127 2.0–2.5 mg cm⁻². Galvanostatic measurements were carried out in CR2032 coin-type
128 cells, while electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and galvanostatic
129 intermittent titration technique (GITT) were performed in three electrode Swagelok-
130 type cell. 1 M NaPF₆ in EC (ethylene carbonate) : DMC (dimethyl carbonate) (1 : 1) was
131 used as the electrolyte, glass fibre D as the separator and metallic Na as the counter and
132 reference electrodes. The electrochemical experiments (charge/discharge profile, EIS
133 and GITT) were carried out at room temperature in the voltage range of 4.2–1.5 V vs.
134 Na⁺/Na at C/10 rate in a VMP3 potentiostat (Bio-Logic). EIS data were recorded in the
135 frequency range of 100 kHz–5 mHz fitted by Boukamp's Equivalent Circuit software.³⁴
136 The used equivalent circuit was already successfully employed for other layered
137 oxides.^{35–39} This model is based on electrolyte resistance (R_{elec}) when Na⁺ ions cross the
138 electrolyte from one electrode to the other and the resistance and capacitance of the

139 electrode/ electrolyte interface (R_{SPL} and C_{SPL}) which both appear in the high-frequency
140 region. At a medium frequency, charge-transfer resistance (R_{CT}) and double layer
141 capacitance (C_{DL}) are observed, while at a low frequency, bulk electronic resistance (R_e)
142 and capacitance arising from charge accumulation at the surface of the particles or at
143 intraparticle crystallite domains (C_e) are observed. Finally, at the lowest frequency
144 region Warburg diffusion (Z_w) linked to the solid-state diffusion of Na^+ ions inside the
145 crystal and the intercalation capacity (C_i) due to the charge accumulation (Fig. S1†) are
146 observed. All resistors and related capacitors are connected in parallel, resulting in an
147 equivalent circuit $R_{elec}(R_{SPL}C_{SPL})(R_{CT}C_{DL})(R_eC_e)Z_wC_i$ in Boukamp's notation. During the
148 fitting procedure, the capacity and Z_w parameters were replaced with a constant phase
149 element (CPE) since electrodes do not follow an ideal behaviour due to the surface
150 inhomogeneity, roughness or degree of polycrystallinity.⁴⁰ For GITT experiments, the
151 applied current was determined by taking into account $C/100$ for 1 hour followed by a
152 relaxation time of 2 hours.

153

154 2.5. Theoretical methods

155 We performed DFT calculations within the Vienna ab initio simulation package.^{41,42} We
156 employed the PBE functional. In order to describe the localized nature of Fe and Mn 3d
157 states, we applied the DFT+U scheme of Dudarev et al., with $U = 4.0$ eV for Fe and Mn
158 atoms as suggested in the literature.^{43,44} All calculations were spin-polarized, starting
159 from a high-spin configuration. We used PBE-based projector augmented wave
160 potentials⁴⁵ to replace core electrons, whereas we treated the Na (3s), Fe (3p, 3d, 4s),
161 Mn (3p, 3d, 4s), Ti (3p, 3d, 4s), and O (2s, 2p) electrons explicitly as valence electrons
162 and their wave functions were expanded in plane waves with a cut-off energy of 600 eV.
163 The irreducible Brillouin zone was sampled using a Monkhorst–Pack⁴⁶ grid with $7 \times 7 \times 1$
164 k-point sampling per (1 x 1) unit cell. Ground state energies for every configuration were
165 computed allowing the lattice parameters, cell shape, and atomic positions to relax with
166 a residual force threshold of $0.02 \text{ eV } \text{\AA}^{-1}$. In the materials' models in this study, we used
167 the Na/Na-vacancy ordering previously found for a range of other P2 phases with 2/3
168 Na content: P2– $Na_{2/3}CoO_2$,⁴⁷ P2– $Na_{2/3}Fe_{2/3}Mn_{1/3}O_2$ ⁴⁸ and P2– $Na_{2/3}Mn_{2/3}Ni_{1/3}O_2$.⁴³ This
169 ordering consists of a zigzag pattern of Na1 and Na2 sites arranged in triangular units,
170 involving a supercell with in-plane lattice vectors $a_{super} = 3a + 2b$ and $b_{super} = 2a + 3b$,
171 containing 24 formula units. It is known that in binary or ternary transition metal P2
172 compounds, the presence of Mn atoms can suppress long-range Na/Na-vacancy
173 ordering.^{49–51} However, from a computational viewpoint, the modelling of such
174 arrangements would require large supercells which are unaffordable at the DFT level.
175 Therefore, the Na/Na vacancy ordering assumed in this work should be considered as a
176 low-energy, reasonable approximation. For the Ti/Fe/Mn ordering in P2–
177 $Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2-x}Ti_xO_2$ oxide layers, we have thoroughly sampled a range of local
178 structures within the considered supercell. In particular, for each investigated Ti
179 composition ($x = 0.0, 0.1, \text{ and } 0.2$) we randomly generated 50 different configurations
180 and computed their DFT energy. The Mn ions were classified as Mn^{III} or Mn^{IV} according
181 to their magnetic moment, 3.8 and 3.2 mB respectively. Additionally, we also saw that
182 Mn^{III} or Mn^{IV} species show a small difference of ca. 0.1e in their Bader charges.⁵²

183

184 2.6. Solid state nuclear magnetic resonance (ss-NMR)

185 ^{23}Na magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance (MAS NMR) experiments were
186 performed at 52.9 MHz on a Bruker-300 spectrometer charged to a field of 4.7 T using a
187 1.3 mm MAS probe. The rotor spinning speeds were set to 50 kHz. A rotor synchronized
188 spin–echo pulse sequence ($90^\circ - t_s - 180^\circ - t^1$ acquisition) was used with a 90° pulse of 1.2
189 ms and a recycle delay of 0.6 seconds. The spectra were referenced to a 0.2 M solution
190 of $^{23}\text{NaCl}$. Signals were deconvoluted using dmfit software.⁵³
191

192 3. Results and discussion

193 3.1. Cooperative Jahn–Teller lattice distortion

194 In order to evaluate the effect of Ti^{IV} substitution on the crystalline structure of the
195 electrode material, we synthesized three $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$ batches with
196 different Ti^{IV} doping levels ($x = 0.0, 0.1, \text{ and } 0.2$). We selected this particular family of
197 layered oxides owing to their good electrochemical performance as reported in the
198 literature combined with the strategic interest of their components.^{14,28} The structure
199 of MnFe and MnFeTi is characterized by AABBA stacking of TMO_2 layers (Fig. 1b). Na^+
200 ions occupy two types of trigonal prismatic sites, either sharing edges (Na1) or faces
201 (Na2) with respect to adjacent oxide layers.⁵⁴ PXRD patterns, in operando synchrotron
202 X-ray diffraction and neutron powder diffraction of MnFe and MnFeTi have been
203 reported by our group in previous publications (see also Fig. S2[†]).^{14,28} Diffraction peaks
204 of both samples are satisfactorily indexed by hexagonal (S.G.: $P6_3/mmc$) symmetry. The
205 PXRD pattern of MnTi has been also fitted by hexagonal symmetry using the same space
206 group (S.G.: $P6_3/mmc$) (Fig. 1c). However, there are some diffraction peaks (e.g., $2\theta =$
207 $38.2^\circ, 42.40^\circ, 47.70^\circ$ and 61.06°) that cannot be indexed (inset of Fig. 1c). Notice that
208 layered oxides can form a range of different polymorphs depending on the synthesis
209 conditions, Na content, and presence of TM vacancies.^{55,56} Additionally, in the case of
210 Mn-based compounds, Kumakura et al. have recently reported that JT active high spin
211 Mn^{III} can induce a lattice distortion from hexagonal (Fig. 1b) to orthorhombic (Fig. 1d)
212 symmetry due to cooperative JT distortion (CJTD).⁵⁷ Since the amount of Mn^{III} in the
213 MnTi sample is higher than that of MnFe and MnFeTi samples (Table S1[†]), it could be
214 said that the observed lattice distortion in MnTi is induced by CJTD. Indeed, when the
215 diffraction pattern of MnTi is refined by orthorhombic symmetry and the $Cmcm$ space
216 group (Fig. 1e) the peaks not indexed by hexagonal symmetry are now satisfactorily
217 adjusted (inset of Fig. 1e). Hence, when Mn is replaced with Ti substitutes in a higher
218 amount than 0.1, the consequent increase of JT-active Mn^{III} in the layers induces a large
219 distortion of the structure that modifies the symmetry. Interestingly, to the best of our
220 knowledge, such a CJTD-induced lattice distortion in a $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{TM}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$
221 composition is reported here for the first time.
222

223

224 Fig. 1. Structure and Rietveld refinement of the $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Ti}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (MnTi) powder by the Rietveld
 225 method. (a) Schematic of Mn^{III} and Mn^{IV} electronic configurations and visualization of Jahn-Teller
 226 distortion: (b) and (c) using hexagonal (S.G.: $P6_3/mmc$) and (d) and (e) using ortho- rhombic (S.G.: $Cmcm$)
 227 symmetry. Insets show the zoom of the powder X-ray diffraction patterns between $2\theta = 35\text{--}65^\circ$.

228 The cell parameters of MnFe and MnFeTi shown in Table S2[†] (crystallographic positions
 229 in Table S3[†]) are in agreement with the already reported values,^{14,28} while the MnTi
 230 sample exhibits values close to orthorhombic $P'2\text{-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{TM}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$.⁵⁷ The average TM–
 231 O distance obtained by Rietveld analysis could provide indirect information about
 232 $[\text{TMO}_6]$ octahedral distortion, considering that only Mn^{III} octahedra should be distorted
 233 by the JT effect and the TM–O distance (Table S2[†]) increases when increasing the
 234 amount of Mn^{III} in the sample ($\text{MnTi} > \text{MnFeTi} > \text{MnFe}$) (Table S1[†]). The octahedra in the
 235 MnTi sample should be the most distorted whilst the octahedra in the MnFe sample will
 236 be less distorted. The higher degree of distortion associated with the octahedra in the
 237 MnTi sample is corroborated by the symmetry change from hexagonal to orthorhombic

238 that leads to two distinct TM–O distances: 1.89 Å (equatorial bonds) and 2.24 Å (axial
239 bonds) (Fig. S3†).

240

241 3.2. Mn and Ti oxidation states in P2–Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2-x}Ti_xO₂ (x = 0.0, 0.1 and 0.2)

242 The Ti substitutions performed in the starting material might lead to different chemical
243 environments for the transition metal atoms. To confirm the oxidation states of Mn and
244 Ti in the MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi samples, XAS measurements have been carried out.
245 Fig. 2a shows the Mn K-edge X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectra of
246 the three samples. The absorption edge position, taken as the first maximum of the
247 derivative spectrum (inset of Fig. 2a), shifts to lower energies with increasing Ti
248 concentration. As shown in Fig. 2b, the comparison of the Mn absorption edge energy
249 vs. the oxidation state of reference Mn oxides (Mn, MnO, Mn₂O₃, Mn₃O₄ and MnO₂)
250 confirms that all the samples contain Mn ions in an oxidation state intermediate
251 between III and IV. The Ti K-edge position, shown in the inset of Fig. S4† (derivative
252 spectra), does not change with the Fe concentration. The comparison with reference Ti
253 oxides⁵⁸ indicates that the mean oxidation state is IV in both the MnFeTi and MnTi
254 samples.

255

256

257 Fig. 2 Mn oxidation state determination. (a) Mn K-edge XANES spectra for MnFe (blue), MnFeTi (red) and MnTi
258 (black). The inset shows the first derivatives of the spectra. (b) XAS Mn K-edge energy vs. the calculated Mn
259 oxidation state for the studied samples (circles) and reference compounds (grey squares).

260 3.3. Role of the Ti substitution degree in P2–Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2-x}Ti_xO₂ (x = 0.0, 0.1 and 0.2)

261 The electrochemical performance of MnFe and MnFeTi has been already reported;
262 however, the electrochemical properties of the two of the studied samples (MnFe and
263 MnFeTi) have been included in Fig. 3 for comparison.^{14,28,59} MnFe shows higher
264 charge/discharge capacities (200/190 mA h g⁻¹) than MnFeTi (146/144 mA h g⁻¹) during
265 the second cycle at C/10 due to the fact that in MnFeTi, both Fe and Ti species are
266 electrochemically inactive within the considered 4.0–2.0 V vs. the Na⁺/Na voltage range
267 (Fe inactivity was confirmed by Mössbauer spectroscopy; see also CV in Fig. S5†) while
268 in the MnFe sample Fe^{III} is electrochemically active.¹⁴ However, after 50 cycles, the
269 charge/discharge capacities of MnFe and MnFeTi reached comparable values of ca. 140
270 mA h g⁻¹. Consequently, the capacity retention after 50 cycles is better for MnFeTi
271 (95.1%) than for MnFe (71.7%). Meanwhile, the galvanostatic charge/discharge profile
272 of MnTi shows a second charge/discharge capacity of 55/52 mA h g⁻¹, with only ca. 0.2
273 Na⁺ ions extracted/inserted per formula unit (C_{theo} = 265.89 mA h g⁻¹). The poor capacity
274 values might be related to the higher number of JT active Mn^{III} since higher octahedral
275 distortion in layered oxides is considered to be a drawback for electrochemical
276 performance.^{13,16,59} Albeit the capacities are very low, MnTi exhibits a good discharge

277 capacity retention of 92% after 50 cycles (Fig. 3b), but lower than the capacity retention
 278 of MnFeTi. This confirms that the structure stabilization effect of Ti^{IV} doping must be
 279 controlled since it can also negatively influence the electrochemical properties. From
 280 Fig. 3, it is clearly observed that a Ti content equal to 0.1 (MnFeTi) yields a balance
 281 between specific charge and capacity retention.
 282

283 Fig. 3. Voltage profile and cycle retention of MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi. (a) Galvanostatic charge/discharge
 284 profile of the 2nd (line) and 50th (dash) cycles. (b) Evolution of the capacity after 50 cycles in the voltage range of
 285 4.0–2.0 V vs. Na^+/Na at C/10.

286 Considering the observed differences in electrochemical performance, we decided to
 287 explore the influence of kinetics. Hence, the diffusion coefficient of Na^+ ions (D_{Na^+}) for
 288 the three samples (MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi) has been determined by GITT (Fig. S6, S7
 289 and S8) using eqn (1).^{†36} Fig. S9[†] shows D_{Na^+} as a function of voltage and reveals similar
 290 profiles to those commonly found in the literature for solid-state diffusion of layered
 291 oxides.^{48,55,60} Interestingly, the three samples exhibit D_{Na^+} values of $10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, up to
 292 3.7 V vs. Na^+/Na . This suggests that Na^+ ion diffusion is not the key factor that
 293 determines the electrochemical properties of the studied samples. The better capacity
 294 retention of the electrode substituted with Ti was previously suggested to improve the
 295 structural stability of layered oxides.^{14,25} In the following sections, we will discuss about
 296 the optimum balance between the Ti^{IV} -induced stability and the increase of Mn^{III} -
 297 induced JT distortion.
 298

299 3.4. Transport properties of $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$

300 The electronic conductivity, interfacial resistance and eventual electrode/electrolyte
 301 interface stability of MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi have been evaluated by means of EIS
 302 experiments. The Nyquist plots of the pristine electrodes are shown in Fig. 4. In general,
 303 the EIS results for the three samples are characterized by a sloping line at frequencies
 304 lower than 25–30 mHz, which is attributed to Na^+ ion diffusion (due to the effect of the
 305 bulk electronic resistance in the low-frequency region, the D_{Na^+} was calculated by GITT).
 306 Additionally, three semicircles are found (cf. Fig. 4 and inset): a large one at low
 307 frequency (LF, <10 Hz) and two smaller ones at medium (MF, 4 kHz–10 Hz) and high
 308 frequency (HF, >4 kHz; see Fig. S10[†] for clarity). In particular, the sloping line for the
 309 MnTi sample is not clearly observed since it is covered by the large LF semicircle found
 310 from 10 Hz to 5 mHz. HF and MF semicircles are attributed to resistances and
 311 capacitances when Na^+ ions cross the electrode/electrolyte interface, defined elsewhere

312 for cathodes as the solid permeable interface (SPI) layer, and the double layer onto
 313 active particles respectively. The LF semicircle is related to the bulk electronic
 314 conductivity of the active material.^{35–37,61} Interestingly, the size of the LF semicircle
 315 increases with the amount of Ti in the sample (drastically in the MnTi sample) suggesting
 316 that MnTi has the lowest electronic conductivity.
 317

318 Fig. 4. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy of the pristine electrode. The Nyquist plot in the frequency
 319 range of 100 kHz–5 mHz for MnFe (blue), MnFeTi (red) and MnTi (black). Inset is the Nyquist plot in the frequency of
 320 100 kHz–5 mHz for MnFe and MnTi samples and 100 kHz–0.15 Hz for the MnTi sample.

321 Taking into account the observed semicircles and sloping line, impedance dispersion
 322 data from pristine electrodes were fitted by the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. S1† and
 323 described in the Experimental section. The equivalent circuit used to fit the EIS data of
 324 intercalation materials is based on the surface layer model proposed by Aurbach et al.⁶²
 325 However, another resistance and capacitance (RC) have been included due to the low
 326 electronic conductivity of the active material. The results are shown in Table S4† and are
 327 similar to those described for other Li and Na layered oxides.^{37,63} As expected, since the
 328 same electrolyte was used in all cases, the electrolyte resistance (R_{elec}) is similar for the
 329 three samples. The SPI layer resistance (R_{SPI}) and charge-transfer resistance (R_{CT}) values
 330 are close in MnFe and MnFeTi samples whilst the MnTi sample shows higher resistance
 331 values; this would be consistent with the poor electrochemical performance of the MnTi
 332 sample. The main differences are observed for the bulk electronic resistance (R_e), with
 333 MnTi displaying a much higher R_e (20406 ohm cm^2) than MnFe (712 ohm cm^2) and
 334 MnFeTi (2370 ohm cm^2). Such a low electronic conductivity of MnTi can be attributed to
 335 the higher content of Ti^{IV} ($3d^0$) which does not have electrons in the conduction band
 336 and in turn result in poor electrochemical properties.
 337

338 Besides analysing the pristine materials, EIS experiments were carried out upon
 339 electrochemical cycling. Fig. 5 shows the Nyquist plots for MnFe (a and b), MnFeTi (c and
 340 d), and MnTi (e and f) during 30 cycles in completely charged (4.2 V vs. Na^+/Na) and
 341 discharged (1.5 V vs. Na^+/Na) states. The overall resistance of all the studied samples is
 342 lower in the charged state (4.2 V; Fig. 5a, c and e) than in the discharged state (1.5 V;
 343 Fig. 5b, d and f). In the discharged state, the amount of Mn^{III} is higher and this could be
 344 the origin of the observed higher resistance values. The overall resistance in the
 345 discharged state in MnFeTi is less than half of the overall resistance of MnFe and MnTi.
 346 This is in agreement with the better electrochemical properties and excellent capacity

347 retention of the MnFeTi sample. The most interesting behaviour is observed in charged
 348 state. First, the MnTi sample provides a large overall resistance, which is in agreement
 349 with the poor electrochemical performance observed in the galvanostatic profile (Fig.
 350 3a). Second, the initial overall resistance values of MnFe are lower than those of MnFeTi,
 351 probably due to the better electronic conductivity observed for the pristine electrode.
 352 Finally, the resistance of MnFe in the charged state gradually increases upon
 353 electrochemical cycling reaching higher values than MnFeTi whilst the latter yields
 354 constant overall resistance values. Such constant resistance values of MnFeTi in both
 355 states (4.2 V and 1.5 V) reflect the observed excellent capacity retention (95.1%) after
 356 50 cycles.
 357

358 Fig. 5 Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and determination of the R_e , R_{CT} , R_{elec} and R_{spi} . Nyquist plots
 359 as a function of electrochemical cycling for (a and b) MnFe, (c and d) MnFeTi and (e and f) MnTi at 4.2 V and 1.5
 360 V vs. Na^+/Na , respectively. The frequency range is 100 kHz–5 mHz. The obtained resistance of MnFe and MnFeTi:
 361 (g) R_e values at 4.2 V vs. Na^+/Na . R_{CT} , R_{elec} and R_{spi} values at (h) 4.2 V and (i) 1.5 V vs. Na^+/Na .

362 In order to better understand the origin of the resistance evolution in these samples,
 363 the components have been independently analysed. To this end, the impedance data
 364 were fitted to the same equivalent circuit used for pristine samples (Fig. S1†). The fitting
 365 was performed for MnFe and MnFeTi. The impedance data of MnTi were not fitted
 366 because of the dominating large semicircle at LFs and the noise at HF/MF. The
 367 resultant resistance values during the first 10 cycles are shown in Fig. 5g–i. The simulated
 368 Nyquist plots of the 1st, 5th and 10th cycles are included as examples in Fig. S11.†
 369

370 The overall resistance of MnFe and MnFeTi samples is dominated by R_e . In the charged
371 state (Fig. 5g), the R_e of MnFeTi after one cycle is six times that of MnFe. However, after
372 ten cycles, the R_e of MnFeTi decreases and quickly stabilizes around 375 ohm cm^2 , while
373 the R_e of MnFe increases without signs of stabilization. The decrease of the bulk
374 electronic conductivity in MnFe might originate from defects in the structure or stacking
375 faults that form during layer gliding involved in the phase transitions upon
376 electrochemical cycling. Interestingly, although such transitions could also occur in
377 MnFeTi, the fact that R_e values do not increase upon cycling suggests that the structural
378 stability of MnFeTi is indeed better than that of MnFe (see Fig. S12,[†] where the lower
379 OP4 phase is formed in Ti substituted samples).

380

381 The trend of R_{CT} , R_{elec} and R_{SPI} in the charged state (4.2 V; Fig. 5h) and discharged state
382 (1.5 V, Fig. 5i) is similar for MnFe and MnFeTi. R_{CT} is twice lower in the charged state
383 than in the discharged state which means that Na^+ ion extraction is easier than insertion.
384 After several cycles, R_{CT} is higher in MnFe than in MnFeTi. Hence, Na^+ ions are easily
385 inserted/extracted into/ from MnFeTi than the MnFe sample during electrochemical
386 cycling indicating also better structural stability.

387

388 R_{elec} values are similar in both MnFe and MnFeTi and they remain constant upon cycling
389 suggesting that the electrolyte is not decomposed to a large extent. This is in good
390 agreement with low R_{SPI} values, which indicate the existence of a thin SPI layer.
391 However, MnFe shows higher R_{SPI} than MnFeTi, implying that more SPI layers are formed
392 upon electrochemical cycling, giving rise to worse structural stability of the active
393 material. Considering that the MnFe layered oxide shows higher volume changes,²⁵ it
394 can be put forward that in each charge/discharge process a new surface of the active
395 particles will be exposed to the electrolyte, with the subsequent reaction and formation
396 of new SPI layers.

397

398 It can be concluded that the poor electrochemical properties of MnTi are originated by
399 its low electronic conductivity, but not by hindered Na^+ ion diffusion. Meanwhile, the
400 unsubstituted MnFe sample shows worse capacity retention than MnFeTi due to the low
401 Ti doping content, helps to stabilize the structure, as manifested by the lower and stable
402 R_e values observed upon electrochemical cycling.

403

404 3.5. Structural determination from ab initio calculations

405 In order to better understand the role of TM doping in the JT effect, statistical analysis
406 of the changes in the crystal structure introduced by the partial substitution of Fe with
407 Ti using density functional theory (DFT) calculations has been carried out so as to analyse
408 the enhanced structural stability of MnFeTi at the molecular level. To this end, a number
409 of different cationic configurations were randomly generated (Fe–Mn–Ti) and their DFT
410 energy was computed. Then, the configurations with energies in the range of the
411 thermal energy at room temperature (25 meV per formula unit from the absolute
412 energy minimum) have been statistically considered. Fig. S13[†] shows the distribution of
413 TM–O distances corresponding to different [TMO6] octahedra in MnFe, MnFeTi, and
414 MnTi (Table S5[†] summarizes the averaged TM–O distances). Notice that all of the Mn^{IV} –
415 O distance distributions are characterized by a single main peak between 1.90 \AA and
416 2.05 \AA , with an average distance of $1.95\text{--}1.96 \text{ \AA}$ independent of the Ti content. However,

417 Mn^{III}–O distributions split into two distinct peaks, one below 2.0 Å and the other one
 418 above 2.2 Å. This splitting is caused by the JT distortion characteristic of ions with an
 419 electronic configuration ((*t2g*)³(*eg*)¹) as Mn^{III}. The first peak corresponds to the four
 420 equatorial short bonds of a distorted [Mn^{III}O₆] octahedron. This is shifted to larger
 421 distances compared with Mn^{IV}–O bonds and its average value slightly decreases with the
 422 Ti^{IV} content. The second Mn^{III}–O peak corresponds to the two axial long distances of the
 423 [Mn^{III}O₆] octahedron and it is significantly affected by the Ti content, with a shift towards
 424 larger distances when increasing the amount of Ti^{IV} in the system. It is seen, therefore,
 425 that the presence of Ti in the structure mainly affects the distortion of [Mn^{III}O₆]
 426 octahedra, by enlarging the Mn^{III}–O axial distance.

427

428 Another key observation is that Ti^{IV}–O distance distributions span over a wide range (ca.
 429 0.4 Å), much wider than any other TM–O distance distribution. This indicates that
 430 [Ti^{IV}O₆] octahedra can easily be distorted in these structures. It is put forward that this
 431 inherent flexibility of [Ti^{IV}O₆] octahedra helps to accommodate the elongation of Mn^{III}–
 432 O axial distances in JT distorted [Mn^{III}O₆] octahedra. In order to gain a deeper insight
 433 into this effect, we computed the distortion index (DI) of [TMO₆] octahedra as a function
 434 of the Ti^{IV} content using the DI expression proposed by Warren (eqn (2)[†]).⁶⁴ Fig. 6 shows
 435 the average value and dispersion range of the DI for each [TMO₆] octahedra. As
 436 expected, the largest distortion corresponds to [Mn^{III}O₆] octahedra due to the JT effect.
 437 Notice that the distortion increases on increasing the Ti content, which can be explained
 438 by the impact of CJTD since the substitution of Fe^{III} with Ti^{IV} necessarily involves an
 439 increase in the number of Mn^{III} ions in the structure. Interestingly, amongst the non-
 440 active JT ions (Mn^{IV}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV}), the DI of [Ti^{IV}O₆] octahedra is about 2–3 times larger than
 441 that of [Fe^{III}O₆] and [Mn^{IV}O₆] octahedra. Again, this highlights the prominent flexibility
 442 of [Ti^{IV}O₆] octahedra, which can effectively help to relieve structural stresses and better
 443 accommodate the intrinsic distortion induced by JT active Mn^{III} ions. [Mn^{IV}O₆] and
 444 [Fe^{III}O₆] octahedra present much lower DI values and standard deviations than [Ti^{IV}O₆]
 445 octahedra, which indicates that they are rather rigid and unable to easily adapt their
 446 geometries to account for distortions.

447

448 Fig. 6 Distortion index of [TMO₆] octahedra as a function of the Ti content for MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi.
 449 Points and bars represent mean values and standard deviations, respectively.

450 Interestingly, it is also observed that the maximal distortion of $[\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}_6]$ octahedra occurs
 451 in the MnFeTi system, while for MnTi the $[\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}_6]$ octahedra are less distorted. To
 452 rationalize this finding, notice again that the number of Mn^{III} ions increases when
 453 moving from MnFeTi to MnTi and, therefore, this suggests that the structural stress
 454 reduction ability of $[\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}_6]$ octahedra cannot compensate the presence of too many
 455 Mn^{III} ions in $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$ structures and that might be the origin of the poor
 456 capacities observed in the galvanostatic profile and the high resistances.

457

458 3.6. Local chemical environment and structure of $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$

459 To gain further insight into the local Mn–O coordination of the MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi
 460 samples, Mn K-edge spectra were collected in the extended energy range (EXAFS). The
 461 k^2 weighted EXAFS signals and the corresponding Fourier transforms (FTs) are shown in
 462 Fig. 7 for the three samples. The first peak of FT at around 1.6 Å corresponds to the first
 463 Mn–O coordination shell while the second peak at around 2.5 Å represents the Mn–Mn
 464 (Fe, Ti) second coordination shell with some contribution from Mn–Na distances. The
 465 similarity of the EXAFS features shows that the presence of Ti does not significantly
 466 affect the local environment of Mn, although a small reduction of the signal amplitude
 467 is observed, possibly related to increased structural disorder in both the first and second
 468 shell. The EXAFS signals were analysed using different models for the Mn–O oxygen
 469 coordination shell. The first peak of FT could not be modelled by assuming a single Mn–
 470 O shell with coordination number 6 (undistorted octahedron) while a distorted (4 + 2)
 471 coordination model with 4 oxygen atoms around 1.94 Å and 2 oxygen atoms around
 472 2.30 Å reproduces the first peak of the FT in agreement with the results of theoretical
 473 simulations.

474

475

476 Fig. 7 Mn K-edge k^2 weighted EXAFS signals: (a) for the three samples namely MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi.
 477 (b) The corresponding Fourier transforms in the $3.7\text{--}11.9\text{ \AA}^{-1}$ window. The grey dashed line is the best fit
 478 with the distorted (4 + 2) coordination model.

479

480 The best-fit curves are reported in Fig. 7b (grey dots), and the resulting structural
 481 parameters are listed in Table S6[†]. These experimental results are compatible with
 482 those of the theoretical calculations (Table S5[†]), although the slightly larger distortion
 483 of the $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{O}_6]$ octahedron with increasing Ti content is not confirmed by present data.
 484 It should be noted however that the EXAFS signals are damped by the effect of both
 485 thermal and static disorders of Mn–O distances resulting in merging of the distribution
 486 of equatorial and axial oxygen for both Mn^{III} and Mn^{IV} sites (same FT peak in Fig. 7a).

487 Therefore, the EXAFS sensitivity to slight changes of the apical distances may be reduced
488 when such disorder effects are taken into account.

489

490 3.7. Dynamic changes induced by Ti^{IV} doping

491 Solid-state NMR experiments were performed on the Ti substituted and unsubstituted
492 samples (P2–Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2-x}Ti_xO₂, x = 0.0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, and 0.2) in order to analyse
493 the structural and dynamic changes induced by Ti^{IV} doping. Among all these samples,
494 the MnFe, MnFeTi and MnTi samples studied throughout the manuscript are included.
495 NMR spectra of paramagnetic materials are generally determined by large paramagnetic
496 shifts that are strongly dependent on the TM–O–Na bond distances and angles as well
497 as on the nature and oxidation state of the paramagnetic element.^{65–70} Particularly, ²³Na
498 solid-state NMR experiments in Na-based P2 layered oxides containing Fe and Mn have
499 been demonstrated to be often characterized by single resonances resulting from the
500 fast motional averaging of Na⁺ ions between the distinct crystallographic sites in the
501 structure.^{66,67} In the case of the unsubstituted P2–Na_{2/3}MnO₂ phase, the ²³Na solid-state
502 NMR spectrum displays more than one signal,¹⁸ indicating that at a high Mn content
503 there is no fast motional exchange of the Na⁺ ions in the structure.

504

505 The solid-state NMR spectrum of MnFe is shown in Fig. 8a. The signal observed at an
506 averaged shift of 1350 ppm could not be satisfactorily fitted by a single resonance and
507 a two-line fitting was required as shown in Fig. 8a. This finding confirms that Na⁺ ions
508 are not fast exchanging with respect to the NMR timescale in this compound, like in the
509 P2–Na_{2/3}MnO₂ sample.¹⁸ This can be ascribed to the Mn^{III} JT distortions which involve
510 Mn^{III}–O bond elongations that can result in stronger electrostatic interactions in the O–
511 Na bonds and consequently in a reduction of the Na⁺ ion exchange rates. The ²³Na solid
512 state NMR spectrum of the Ti-doped material with 5% Ti^{IV} shows one signal that could
513 be deconvoluted considering a single resonance, which is represented by the red line in
514 the spectrum (Fig. 8a). This indicates that fast Na⁺ ion exchange processes are present
515 in the Ti doped compound resulting in a motional averaged single resonance in the NMR
516 spectrum. This experimentally corroborates that the structural changes resulting from
517 the CJTD in the MnFe material are lightened in the Ti-doped compound resulting in
518 faster Na⁺ exchange rates in the structure. The superposition of the ²³Na solid-state NMR
519 spectra of the MnFe compound and 5% Ti^{IV}-doped samples (P2–
520 Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.15}Ti_{0.05}O₂), in addition to the linewidth changes, clearly indicates a shift of
521 the signal of the Ti-doped sample. The presence of this shift towards lower paramagnetic
522 values is due to the effect that partial substitution of a paramagnetic TM (Fe^{III}) with a
523 diamagnetic cation (Ti^{IV}) has on the overall paramagnetic interactions influencing the Na
524 population. It is worth highlighting that the shift is homogeneous, demonstrating that
525 Na⁺ ions are rapidly moving throughout the entire alkali layer, and, therefore, Ti^{IV}-doping
526 impacts the entire Na population even at such low Ti^{IV} concentrations (5%). A similar
527 result was previously observed for the MnFeTi composition, demonstrating that Ti^{IV}
528 substitution is homogeneous in this material.¹⁴

530 Fig. 8. ^{23}Na solid state NMR spectra. (a) MnFe fitted considering two lines (top), the spectrum of the Ti
 531 doped compound $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.15}\text{Ti}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ fitted using a single line (centre) and both spectra
 532 superimposed (bottom); signals marked by (*). (b) Spectra of $\text{P2-Na}_{0.67}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$ ($x = 0.0, 0.05, 0.1,$
 533 0.15 and 0.2). (c) The linewidths of the signals shown in (b) are plotted as a function of Ti-doping. The
 534 linewidth of the parent compound MnFe is calculated as the weighted average of the signals used for the
 535 deconvolution of this spectrum. (d) ^{23}Na -NMR shifts of the spectra shown in (b) are plotted as function of
 536 Ti-doping, and the shifts were calculated as the centre of mass of the observed resonances.

537

538 In order to understand in detail the impact of Ti doping in the Na population, the ^{23}Na
 539 solid state NMR analysis was extended to the intermediate compositions with a higher
 540 Ti^{IV} content: $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_2$ ($x = 0.1, 0.15$ and 0.2). The resulting spectra are
 541 shown superimposed in Fig. 8b. A continuous decrease of the ^{23}Na NMR shift is observed
 542 on increasing the Ti^{IV} content. The experimental paramagnetic ^{23}Na -NMR shifts plotted
 543 as a function of Ti composition (Fig. 8b) are well fitted considering a linear correlation.
 544 Due to the additive nature of the paramagnetic interactions in NMR,^{68,69,71} the slope of
 545 this curve is a function of the particular paramagnetic shift that a single Ti^{IV} to Fe^{III}
 546 substitution will create in the ^{23}Na -NMR spectrum. Notice also that although each
 547 spectrum can be simulated considering a single resonance (Fig. 8a), its width is also
 548 linearly growing when the Ti amount is increased as shown by the solid line fitting in Fig.
 549 8b. In Fig. 8c and d the signal linewidths are represented vs. the amount of Ti^{IV} . These
 550 linewidths can be generally correlated with the rate and homogeneity of the exchange
 551 processes, as they can lead to a partial averaging of the anisotropic interactions
 552 responsible for the line-broadening.⁷² Therefore, the observed linewidth increment at a
 553 high Ti^{IV} content can be attributed to the increased JT distortions that are introduced
 554 when Ti^{IV} cations substitute Fe^{III} ions, as this is coupled to an increase in the Mn^{III}
 555 population subject to JT distortions. A balance is thus necessary between two threshold
 556 compositions, where on one side the starting material $\text{P2-Na}_{2/3}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ exhibits two

557 clear resonances indicating the presence of segregated Na⁺ ion populations in slow
558 exchange and on the other side, at high Ti^{IV} contents, the Mn^{III} enrichment results in a
559 reduction of the Na⁺ ion exchange rates. It is well-known that Na⁺ ion exchange is a very
560 important factor correlated to the performance of the electrode material. We therefore
561 consider that the minimum of linewidth found in the 5–10 Ti^{IV}% composition range (Fig.
562 8c) is in line with the experimental observations and DFT calculations detailed in the
563 previous sections where an optimum point in the material performance is found at a Ti^{IV}
564 amount of around 10%.

565

566 4. Conclusions

567 The role of the Jahn–Teller distortions resulting from Ti^{IV} doping in the stabilization of
568 NIB cathode materials such as P2–Na_{2/3}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2-x}Ti_xO₂ layered oxides has been
569 unambiguously identified. The Ti^{IV} octahedra are flexible and can be easily distorted so,
570 for a given concentration of Ti^{IV}, they effectively stabilize the crystal structure of layered
571 oxides by absorbing both strains originating during the cycling process and the
572 distortions resulting from the presence of JT-active Mn^{III} ions. The optimum TM
573 substitution level has been estimated to be around 10% Ti^{IV} which leads to the best
574 electrochemical properties: an excellent capacity retention of >95% and stable
575 resistance values upon electrochemical cycling. However, when a higher amount of Ti
576 (>10%) substitutes Mn, the amount of JT active Mn^{III} ions increases. This leads to a JT
577 destabilization of the crystal structure and to a reduction of the Na⁺ ion mobility that
578 the flexible nature of [Ti^{IV}O₆] octahedra cannot sustain anymore. Consequently, a
579 symmetry transformation occurs, which yields an orthorhombic-symmetry phase with
580 poor electrochemical properties, mainly due to low bulk electronic conductivity. The
581 possibility of maximizing the cycling stability of NIBs by controlling the allowed JT
582 distortion degree of electrode materials opens a whole new range of opportunities in
583 terms of Na-based electroactive material design that could cover all requirements
584 needed for NIB commercialization.

585

586 Author contributions

587 M. Z. and E. G. performed the experiments – synthesis, XRD, and electrochemistry –
588 galvanostatic cycling, GITT, EIS, and sample preparation for XAS, analyzed the data and
589 wrote the manuscript. M. P.: EIS measurements and data analysis. F. N.: supervision of
590 EIS and GITT analysis. M. C., A. T. and A. C.: EXAFS and XANES data analysis and support
591 in sample preparation. O. L., N. A. K, and J. C.: simulation and modelling studies. G. A:
592 performed the XANES and EXAFS measurement at the Elettra Synchrotron facility. J. M.
593 L. A.: NMR studies. M. A. M. M.: designed the experiments, supervised the data analysis
594 and edited the manuscript. T. R.: edited the manuscript and supervised the project. All
595 authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

596

597

598 Conflicts of interest

599 There are no conflicts to declare.

600

601

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